

Does The Universe has Limits? 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, and in particular the ever increasing packet of universes, author analyze the question of universe borders. On one hand, the manifold is finite object in an infinite set of distinct object of the same class, on the other hand, due to mutual interaction in areas of extremum curvatures, the finite object is ever increasing to infinity. Two predictions are made regarding flatness and universe temperature overtime.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T thesis fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The question at the heart of this essay is whether the manifold, i.e. the universe has borders. It is finite or infinite in its nature? according to the above framework, Since it is a defined object within a set of distinct objects of the same class, a set of universes which flatten each other and interact at areas of extremum curvatures, it is finite. On the other hand, since the interaction is ever accruing causing the matrix tensor between those areas of extremum curvatures to expand from them, in that sense the finite object is varying in size and ever increasing, aspiring to infinity. So according to the 8T, similar ideas suggest by scientists of the 20-th century, the manifold is closed, but it has no limit. If one is correct it was Einstein who suggested that definition. It is finite, but aspiring to infinity due to the pressure exerted from other manifolds. We can make a prediction according to this new framework;

Prediction (1): The degree of universe flatness is proportional to time.

Prediction (2): The degree of universe flatness is inversely proportional to temperature

The first prediction is rooted in the idea that the packet is ever increasing in size, new manifolds are getting into the packet and getting flattened, the pressure as a result is increasing in moderate amounts overtime, and the degree of flatness should be varying aspiring complete flatness overtime, meaning that there is a direct correlation between the temporal segment and the flatness. Since that is irreversible process, the universe will keep on expanding, the more flat it is, the weaker the interactions it has according to the primordial, those interactions are accruing at mega scale fermion clusters, as the total variations are immensely large, causing the relationship between net to total to aspire zero.

$$\frac{N_V}{T_V} \rightarrow R \quad (2.2)$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \rightarrow 0$$

The second prediction is rooted in thermodynamics, over larger surface there is less collisions, less mutual interactions, the entities are getting smaller in mass, due to the Quark mass series, and the interactions are getting weaker and more rare. That is synonymous as one believes, with lower temperatures.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)